

The wedding experience: Results of a student design workshop

In preparation of this conference, a student design competition was recently organized. In this competition, four student design teams explored the relationship between emotions and product design. Each team was a mix of students from the Faculty of Industrial Design Engineering of Delft University, the Design Academy Eindhoven and the Faculty of Art, Media & Technology of the Utrecht School of the Arts. The best teams of this competition will present and explain their designs at the conference

The theme of the competition was a wedding. Of course, each person present at a wedding experiences the event in a different manner depending on his or her relationship to the bridal couple and the other guests. Students were asked to design a product for a particular character present at the wedding, which can record and playback this person's experience of the event. This experi-

ence capturer-releaser is to reflect the emotions of the user both in its appearance and interaction. The characters chosen by the four teams are as follows:

1. the ex-wife of the groom
2. the father of the bride
3. the 5-7 year old daughter of the bride
4. the siamese twin of the bride

While some of these characters are realistic and some are extreme, all of them are emotionally complex. At this presentation we hope to see product concepts which reflect the subtleties in the characters.

